

A Clinical Study of Nail Changes in Papulosquamous DisorderSyed Fiaz Hussain¹, Vibhu D^{2*}, B. Janardhan³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology Venereology and Leprosy, Bhaskar Medical College and General Hospital, Yenkapally Village Moinabad Mandal Hyderabad²Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology Venereology and Leprosy, Bhaskar Medical College and General Hospital, Yenkapally Village Moinabad Mandal Hyderabad³Professor and Head of Department of Dermatology Venereology and Leprosy, Bhaskar Medical College and General Hospital, Yenkapally Village Moinabad Mandal Hyderabad

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Abstract:**Background:** Nail changes are frequently associated with various dermatological conditions, including papulosquamous disorders, and serve as an important diagnostic tool. Specific alterations in the nails can provide vital clues to differentiate between different papulosquamous diseases. However, the extent and type of nail changes vary among disorders, and understanding these differences is essential for effective diagnosis and management.**Aim and Objectives:** This study aims to assess the clinical significance of nail changes in patients with papulosquamous disorders and correlate them with disease severity.**Materials and Method:** A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 60 patients diagnosed with papulosquamous disorders, attending the dermatology outpatient clinic. A thorough clinical examination of the nails was performed, and findings were documented. Specific nail changes such as pitting, subungual hyperkeratosis, onycholysis, and others were noted. The severity of nail involvement was correlated with the severity of the underlying disorder using established clinical criteria.**Results and Observations:** Nail changes were most frequently observed in psoriasis (60%), followed by lichen planus (16.7%) and pityriasis rubra pilaris (10%). The most common nail findings included pitting. A strong correlation was observed between the extent of nail involvement and the severity of the underlying disease.**Conclusion:** Nail changes form an integral part of papulosquamous disorder manifestations and are more prevalent in psoriasis, lichen planus, and pityriasis rubra pilaris. Clinicians should consider nail examination an essential part of the diagnostic process to guide effective disease management.**Keywords:** Papulosquamous Disorders, Nail Changes, Psoriasis, Lichen Planus, Pityriasis Rubra Pilaris, Subungual Hyperkeratosis, Pitting.

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Introduction

Papulosquamous disorders, a diverse group of dermatological conditions, are characterized by the presence of papules (raised lesions) and scales. These disorders encompass a variety of conditions such as psoriasis, lichen planus, pityriasis rosea, and seborrheic dermatitis, each with distinct clinical presentations and underlying pathophysiology. While the skin manifestations of these disorders are well-documented and studied, nail involvement, an often overlooked aspect, can serve as a crucial indicator of disease severity and progression.

Nail changes in papulosquamous disorders can range from subtle alterations to more severe deformities, affecting both the appearance and function of the nails. These changes may present as pitting, onycholysis, subungual hyperkeratosis, or even complete nail dystrophy, depending on the

underlying disorder. The impact of nail involvement extends beyond cosmetic concerns, often leading to significant discomfort, functional impairment, and a reduced quality of life for affected individuals.

The recognition and evaluation of nail changes in patients with papulosquamous disorders are essential for comprehensive disease management. Nail involvement can often precede or accompany skin lesions, serving as an early diagnostic clue and helping in the differentiation of these disorders. Despite their clinical significance, nail changes in papulosquamous disorders are frequently underreported or inadequately addressed in clinical practice.

This study aims to systematically investigate and document the nail changes associated with various papulosquamous disorders, providing insights into

their prevalence, patterns, and clinical implications. By enhancing the understanding of these nail manifestations, the study seeks to improve diagnostic accuracy, facilitate earlier intervention, and contribute to the holistic management of patients with papulosquamous disorders.

Materials and Method

This clinical study was designed as a cross-sectional observational study. The study was conducted over a period of one year at the Department of dermatology venereology and leprosy. Bhaskar Medical College and General Hospital, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee and meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The study included 60 patients who presented to the dermatology outpatient clinic with clinically confirmed diagnoses of papulosquamous disorders. These included patients with psoriasis, lichen planus, pityriasis rosea, seborrheic dermatitis, and other related conditions. Patients were enrolled consecutively over the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with clinically diagnosed papulosquamous disorders who presented with nail changes were included in the study.
- Patients who gave consent for study were included

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other dermatological conditions or systemic diseases that could affect the nails, such as fungal infections, diabetes, or peripheral vascular disease, were excluded.

Method

A detailed history was taken from each patient, including the duration and progression of the papulosquamous disorder, any history of systemic illness, and treatment history. A thorough clinical examination was performed, focusing on the skin and nails. Nail changes were documented, including pitting, onycholysis, subungual hyperkeratosis, nail plate discoloration, and dystrophy. High-resolution photographs of the affected nails were taken for further analysis.

In cases where the diagnosis was uncertain, a skin biopsy was performed to confirm the papulosquamous disorder. Nail scrapings and clippings were collected for mycological examination to rule out fungal infections. Routine blood investigations were also conducted to rule out systemic involvement.

Statistical Analysis

The data were entered into a structured database and analyzed using statistical software. The frequency and type of nail changes were determined for each papulosquamous disorder. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings, and chi-square tests were applied to assess the significance of associations between nail changes and specific disorders.

Observation and Results

The study included 60 patients who presented to the dermatology outpatient clinic with clinically confirmed diagnoses of papulosquamous disorders. These included patients with psoriasis, lichen planus, pityriasis rosea, seborrheic dermatitis, and other related conditions and their observations are as given below.

Table 1 : Distribution of demographic profile.

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20 - 30 Years	7	11.7
31 -40 years	29	48.3
41 -50 years	20	33.3
> 50 years	4	6.7
Gender		
Male	31	51.7
Female	29	48.3
Comorbid-Conditions		
Diabetes Mellitus	9	15
Hypertension	15	25
Arthritis	6	10
No conditions	30	50

We have observed that, majority of the patients were from 31 – 40 years of age group, followed by 41 – 50 years of age, there were more number of males were present In the study and, 25% of the cases were observed hypertensive followed by diabetes mellitus and arthritis.

Table 2 : Distribution of diagnosis among study population

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Psoriasis	36	60
Lichen planus	10	16.7
Pityriasis rubra pilaris	6	10
Pityriasis rosea	3	5
Lichen Niditus	2	3.3
Lichen striatus	2	3.3
Parapsoriasis	1	1.7

Table 3 : Distribution of time interval and nail changes among diagnosed cases

Papulosquamous disorders	Time interval between onset of skin lesion and nail disease	Most common nail change in each disorder
Psoriasis	5.3 Years	Pitting of nails
Lichen planus	1.6 years	Thinning of nail plate
Pityriasis rubra pilaris	4 Months	Nail plate thickening
Pityriasis rosea	3 Months	Beau's Line
Lichen Niditus	3 Months	Leukonychia
Lichen striatus	4 Months	Longitudinal striation
Parapsoriasis	1.2 Years	Beau's Line

Discussion

The papulosquamous disorders have gained considerable importance due to the sheer number of cases seen in the daily practice. All of them present with papules, scaly plaques or patches, leading to a clinical dilemma on arriving upon an accurate diagnosis. Distinguishing each disease becomes the need of the hour as treatment and prognosis for each is specific. As most of the papulosquamous disorders have nail changes with specific patterns, a thorough examination of all the 20 nails will definitely help to distinguish that particular papulosquamous disorder and manage accordingly.

A total of 60 patients with papulosquamous disorders presenting with nail changes were included in this study, comprising of 31 males (51.7%) and 29 females (48.3%). Our study has a male preponderance which correlated with the study done by Armesto et al. [1] in which about 661 patients 47.4% had nail involvement, and male preponderance of 13.5%. In the present study majority of the patients were from age groups of 31 – 40 years. This correlated with the study done by David BG et al., where about 39 were males and 11 were females in 50 cases of papulosquamous disorders with nail changes [2]. But their mean age was 46.5 years.

In the present study, psoriasis was the most common papulosquamous disorder which correlates with many previous studies done on this topic of interest [3-5]. Al-Mutairi N et al. [6] studied that nail pitting was found to be the most common manifestation (61.84%) followed by onycholysis (30.26%), and discolouration of the nail plate (7.9%). In our study common nail changes observed worth psoriasis were pitting. Nail pitting was the commonest nail deformation observed in a study done by De Jong et

al. [7] They surveyed 1728 psoriasis patients, among which 51% of patients presented pitting of the nails correlated with our study.

Nail psoriasis affects the finger nails more commonly than toe nail [8]. In a study, on nail psoriasis by Ghosal A et al., 38% finger nail and 26% toe nail involvement were noted. Similar findings were observed in this study [4]. Characteristics of nail psoriasis begin principally after the onset of skin lesions [8]. In this study, the time interval between onset of skin lesion and nail lesion for psoriasis was 5.3 years; whereas it was nine and 11.5 years in studies by Klaassen KM et al., and Vander Velden HM et al., respectively [3,9].

In this study, out of 10 cases of LP, 7(70%) patients had nail changes. The characteristic nail changes observed were thinning. In a study by Scher RK and Fischbein R; 10% of patients affected by nail lichen planus had trachyonychia or twenty nail dystrophy [10]. In pityriasis rubra pilaris patients of this study, the most common nail changes observed were thickening of nail plate, pitting and subungual hyperkeratosis which is comparable to the study by Mortimer PS and Dawber RP; [11]. Most common nail involved were great toe nails of both feet. In this study, only one patient of parapsoriasis and pityriasis lichenoides chronic had nail changes presenting as Beau's line involving the thumb nail and great toe nail.

Conclusion

From above results and observation and after discussion with other studies we can concluded that, Nails, being an essential appendage, play a significant role in various skin conditions and serve as a diagnostic tool. The importance of nail changes in relation to papulosquamous disorders is well

recognized. Specific alterations in the nails allow clinicians to distinguish between different papulosquamous conditions. By correlating these nail changes, dermatologists can make a definitive diagnosis and provide effective treatment. It has been observed that nail changes are more frequently associated with psoriasis, lichen planus, and pityriasis rubra pilaris among papulosquamous disorders. Pitting and subungual hyperkeratosis are the most commonly observed nail patterns. Nail changes are an integral aspect of papulosquamous disease manifestations, with the extent of involvement correlating with disease severity.

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Conflict of Interest : None

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